

Solubility Method for showing Specific Interaction

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Specific interaction of *m*-dinitrobenzene with naphthalene, phenanthrene and anthracene molecules has been studied in carbon tetrachloride. Solubility measurements of *m*-dinitrobenzene in carbon tetrachloride indicate that the magnitude of the parameter A_{13} decreases when small amounts of hydrocarbon molecules are added in the solvent. The addition of hydrocarbon molecules in the solvent, obviously creates some sites which are capable of specific interaction and, therefore, the value of the interaction parameter comes out to be very much lower.

The partial molal heat of mixing, $\overline{\Delta H}_1$, in a regular solution is given by equation (1)

$$\overline{\Delta H}_1 = V_1 (C_{11} + C_{1j} - 2C_{ij}) \varphi_j^2 \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where C_{11} , C_{ij} and C_{jj} represent the energies of interaction (per ml) for like and unlike pairs, V is the molar volume and φ is the volume fraction of the respective component. When interaction between unlike molecules is given by the geometric mean rule, i.e., $C_{ij} = (C_{11} C_{jj})^{1/2}$, then the term $(C_{11} + C_{jj} - 2C_{ij})$ reduces to $(C_{11}^{1/2} - C_{jj}^{1/2})^2$ or replacing $C^{1/2}$ by δ to $(\delta_1 - \delta_j)^2$. The failure of C_{ij} to follow the geometric mean rule denotes the specific interaction between either like or unlike pairs as the case may be.

Hildebrand¹ has shown that the partial molal heat of mixing of a component in a ternary system is given by equation (2)

$$\overline{\Delta H}_1 = V_1 [A_{12} \varphi_2^2 + A_{13} \varphi_3^2 + (A_{12} + A_{13} - A_{23}) \varphi_2 \varphi_3] \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where $A_{ij} = C_{11} + C_{jj} - 2C_{ij}$.

In the case of a regular solution where different magnitudes of forces between like and unlike pairs have no ordering on their rearrangement, the partial molal heat of mixing $\overline{\Delta H}_{sp}$ of a component is given by equation (3)

$$\overline{\Delta H}_{sp} = V_1 [(\delta_1 - \delta_2)^2 \varphi_2^2 + (\delta_1 - \delta_3)^2 \varphi_3^2 + 2(\delta_1 - \delta_2)(\delta_1 - \delta_3) \varphi_2 \varphi_3] \quad (3)$$

The partial molal heat of mixing is also related to the observed solubility, x , and the ideal solubility, a , by the equation (4).

$$RT \ln a/x = \overline{\Delta H}_{sp} \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

The two heats of mixing of equation (3) and (4) are the same. They have been designated as $\overline{\Delta H}_{sp}$ and $\overline{\Delta H}_{sc}$ because former refers to the quantity determined using interaction parameters and the latter using saturation activity methods.

The solubility, x , of equation (4) is determined experimentally, while the ideal solubility, a , is calculated using the expression (5)

$$\ln a = \frac{H_f (T_m - T)}{R T_m T} \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

H_f is the heat of fusion and T_m is the temperature of fusion.

If, on comparison, the two heats of mixing, ΔH_{sp} and $\Delta \overline{H}_{sa}$ are not the same, obviously then the interaction parameter values are in error and C_{ij} cannot be given by simplified geometric mean rule. The higher values of $\Delta \overline{H}_{sp}$ indicate some interaction which has given a low value for the interaction parameter.

In the present investigations, the solubility determinations of *m*-dinitrobenzene (Comp. I) have been carried out in pure carbon tetrachloride (Comp. III) and also in carbon tetrachloride containing small amounts of hydrocarbons (Comp. II). From these two sets of data in binary and ternary systems, the values of $\Delta \overline{H}_{sa}$ have been calculated. Assuming that the value of the interaction parameter $(\delta_1 - \delta_2)^2$ remains constant in both binary and ternary systems, $\Delta \overline{H}_{sp}$ values in equation (3) have been estimated. From the differences in the values of $\Delta \overline{H}_{sa}$ and $\Delta \overline{H}_{sp}$, it has been shown that specific interaction has taken place.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the compounds used were obtained from B.D.H. or Eastman Kodak. The compounds were further purified by recrystallisation from absolute alcohol. Anthracene was purified by sublimation and carbon tetrachloride was distilled after drying over calcium chloride.

The solubilities were determined by synthetic method². This method consisted in observing the solution temperature of systems containing known mole fractions. The soda glass ampule containing known amounts of solute and solvent was sealed. It was then heated to dissolve all the solid and then cooled quickly by immersing in a freezing mixture of dry ice and acetone. On account of sudden cooling the solid was precipitated in the form of fine crystals. The ampule was again warmed slowly in a water bath and the temperature at which last crystal dissolved was noted. A mean of several freezing and melting temperatures, gave the solution temperature. The maximum error in the solution temperature is ± 0.1 . The rate of increase of temperature was maintained less than 0.4°C per minute.

OBSERVATIONS AND DISCUSSION

The molar volume of *m*-dinitrobenzene was estimated from the data given by Jager³. The following table (I) summarises critical data used in all the subsequent calculations.

TABLE I
Critical Data

Component	Molar volume at 25°.	H_f^4 cal.	T_m	' α' ' at 25°
<i>m</i> -dinitrobenzene	118	4160	363.08	12*
Naphthalene	123	—	—	9.8
Anthracene	160	—	—	9.9
Phenanthrene	168	—	—	9.9

* Calculated with the help of Hildebrand rule as given in his book (Reference 1).

2. Samayaajula and Palli: *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1964, 58, 417.

3. Jager: *Z. anorganische Chemie*, 1947, 101, 113.

From the solubility measurements, interaction parameter values at different temperatures have been determined and recorded in table (II). This parameter was found to be temperature dependent. This parameter was not determined at every temperature and, therefore, the values of it which have been used in ternary system calculations, are those which were near to the experimental temperature.

Solubility data of *m*-dinitrobenzene in carbon tetrachloride are represented in fig. (1). Plot of $\log x$ against $1/T$ is a straight line. This was not surprising as the solutions were fairly dilute. The dipoles are surrounded entirely by solvent molecules and as such the relative orientations between the dipoles are not important, the interaction energy, therefore, follows the geometric mean rule.

FIG 1. Solubility and Temperature Relationship
m-dinitrobenzene in carbon tetrachloride.

TABLE II

Solubility of *m*-dinitrobenzene in carbon tetrachloride

Solution temperature in C.	Solubility of <i>m</i> -dinitrobenzene in molefraction	Φ^2_3	$RT \ln a/x = \frac{\Delta H_{32}}{T}$	$V_1(\delta_1 - \delta_2)^2$
30.4	0.03024	0.0283	1611 cal/e	1736
30.8	0.02854	0.0325	1617 "	1735
36.2	0.02531	0.0391	1642 "	1748
35.6	0.02452	0.0414	1652 "	1756
32.6	0.02076	0.0501	1697 "	1786
30.2	0.01770	0.0577	1746 "	1823
28.4	0.01480	0.0642	1760 "	1825
23.8	0.01326	0.0680	1788 "	1847
23.0	0.01242	0.0700	1793 "	1849

In ternary systems, the partial molal heat of mixing $\overline{\Delta H_{m3}}$ of *m*-dinitrobenzene from the solubility data has been calculated and recorded in column 4 of the tables (III to V). $\overline{\Delta H_{sp}}$ is estimated indirectly using equation (3). In equation (3), the first term containing the volume fraction of the donor has been made small in these observations and it never exceeded the order of 10^{-2} . This term will, therefore, be neglected and the maximum error in doing so will be of the order of 2 cal. The second term containing the volume fraction of the solvent is most important. This means that in the partial molal heat of mixing, the major contribution will be due to the interaction between *m*-dinitrobenzene and the solvent molecules. This gives an opportunity to study the variation in the magnitude of parameter A_{13} or $(\delta_1 - \delta_3)^2$ when the solvent lattice has changed slightly due to the presence of small amounts of hydrocarbon. The contribution due to the third term of the equation (3) is positive in the present case, since δ_1 for *m*-dinitrobenzene has a value in the neighbourhood of 12 which is greater than δ_2 and δ_3 .

TABLE III
System: *m*-dinitrobenzene—phenanthrene—carbon tetrachloride

Solution temperature in °C.	Mole fraction of phenanthrene	Mole fraction of <i>m</i> -dinitrobenzene	$RT \ln a/x = \overline{\Delta H_{m3}}$	$V_1 (\delta_1 - \delta_2)^2 \Phi_3^2 > \overline{\Delta H_{sp}}^*$
38.0	0.01359	0.02658	1450 cal	1614 cal
36.8	0.00925	0.03173	1615 "	1667 "
30.2	0.01440	0.02040	1661 "	1674 "
29.0	0.00484	0.02022	1643 "	1660 "
25.4	0.01358	0.01973	1696 "	1664 "

TABLE IV
System: *m*-dinitrobenzene—naphthalene—carbon tetrachloride

Solution temperature in °.	Mole fraction of naphthalene	Mole fraction of <i>m</i> -dinitrobenzene	$RT \ln a/x = \overline{\Delta H_{m3}}$	$V_1 (\delta_1 - \delta_2)^2 \Phi_3^2 > \overline{\Delta H_{sp}}^*$
38.4	0.01913	0.03421	1500 cal	1540 cal
37.0	0.01102	0.03023	1549 "	1576 "
37.0	0.02018	0.03283	1604 "	1567 "
32.8	0.01342	0.02406	1599 "	1622 "
26.0	0.00996	0.01632	1714 "	1710 "

TABLE V
System: *m*-dinitrobenzene—anthracene—carbon tetrachloride

Solution temperature in °C	Mole fraction of anthracene	Mole fraction of <i>m</i> -dinitrobenzene	$RT \ln a/x = \overline{\Delta H_{m3}}$	$V_1 (\delta_1 - \delta_2)^2 \Phi_3^2 > \overline{\Delta H_{sp}}^*$
33.6	0.00823	0.02473	1608 cal	1634 cal
32.8	0.00138	0.02173	1635 "	1670 "
29.0	0.00104	0.01703	1715 "	1738 "
26.0	0.00436	0.01627	1715 "	1734 "
24.0	0.00690	0.01515	1714 "	1748 "

* $\overline{\Delta H_{sp}}$ values have been estimated by neglecting the first and the third term of equation (3). The value for the second term is obtained from Table II. Actual values should have been greater on account of positive contributions of neglected terms.

In spite of the fact, that the exact evaluation of the first and the third terms of the equation (3) has not been possible, a smaller heat of mixing has been found in ternary system, *m*-dinitrobenzene—hydrocarbon—carbon tetrachloride, than could be calculated in binary system—dinitrobenzene—carbon tetrachloride, with the help of solubility measurements. This is enough to indicate in a qualitative way that with the introduction of hydrocarbon molecules in solvent lattice, some sites have been created which are capable of specific interaction. On account of this interaction some energy is released, thereby, decreasing the partial molal heat of mixing. If a system is found in which the first and the third terms of equation (3) are completely known, one can then get a precise knowledge about the formation constant and the heat of formation of the complex formed as a result of interaction. Such data could only be obtained in such systems using spectrophotometric measurements. A check can then be made on the two methods of studying interaction. In the light of the results it can be concluded that parameter A_{13} must decrease as a result of interaction as compared to its value given by the geometric mean rule.

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